

ENHANCING STUDENTS' CREATIVITY AND CONCEPTUAL UNDERSTANDING THROUGH DESIGN THINKING-BASED LEARNING ACTIVITY SHEETS IN GENERAL BIOLOGY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17639134>

ABSTRACT

Design Thinking–Based Learning Activity Sheet (DT-LAS) is a supplementary learning resource that integrates an iterative, human-centered approach emphasizing empathy, ideation, prototyping, and testing to enhance creativity and conceptual understanding. This study examined the effectiveness of DT-LAS in improving the creativity and conceptual understanding of General Academic Strand students at Bukidnon National High School during the School Year 2025–2026, where thirty-six (36) students utilized DT-LAS and thirty-eight (38) students used Non-DT-LAS. A quasi-experimental research design employing a pretest-posttest format was used. An adapted creativity rubric and a validated 50-item teacher-made conceptual understanding test with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.94 served as instruments. Descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were used to determine students' levels of creativity and conceptual understanding, while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was employed to identify significant differences between groups. Findings showed that students exposed to DT-LAS significantly improved in creativity, achieving very high levels in fluency, flexibility, originality, and elaboration, compared to moderate gains in the Non-DT-LAS group. ANCOVA confirmed a significant difference in creativity, indicating that DT-LAS effectively fosters higher-order creative thinking through engaging, learner-centered activities. Both groups showed slight improvement in conceptual understanding, but posttest scores remained within the Did Not Meet Expectations range, with no significant difference between them. While DT-LAS fosters creativity, structured guidance is needed to achieve measurable gains in biological understanding. With these findings, teachers

are encouraged to adopt the Design Thinking–Based Learning Activity Sheet (DT-LAS) to foster creativity, innovation, and deeper conceptual learning among students.

Keywords: *creativity, conceptual understanding, design-thinking, learning activity sheets*

INTRODUCTION

In the 21st century, education goes beyond the mere mastery of academic content; it also requires the development of higher-order thinking skills, including creativity, critical thinking, and conceptual understanding, which are crucial for success in STEM fields (Panergayo & Prudente, 2024). These skills equip learners to tackle complex, real-world problems and actively contribute to an innovation-driven global economy. To support the development of these competencies, many schools implement Learning Activity Sheets (LAS) as supplemental tools, especially in modular and blended learning settings. However, traditional LAS often emphasize procedural exercises and rote memorization, limiting opportunities for creativity and deep learning. This challenge is reflected in international assessments, as Filipino students score significantly below OECD averages in both creative thinking and science performance (Angelo, 2024; OECD, 2023), highlighting a critical need for instructional strategies that effectively promote higher-order thinking and meaningful engagement in science education.

Traditional Learning Activity Sheets (LAS), widely used in the Philippines to support structured and independent learning (Reyes & Caballes, 2021), often focus on factual recall and procedural tasks, limiting opportunities for creativity, critical thinking, and meaningful application. This limitation is exacerbated by the emphasis on standardized testing, which reduces opportunities for inquiry and open-ended problem-solving (Bautista, 2023). Integrating Design Thinking (DT) a human-centered, iterative process of empathy, ideation, prototyping, and testing into LAS offers a promising solution by transforming traditional worksheets into tools that foster innovation, engagement, and deeper conceptual understanding. At the local level, General Academic Strand (GAS) students at Bukidnon National High School struggle to creatively understand and apply biology concepts, highlighting the urgent need for DT-LAS that combine student-centered learning with conceptual rigor and creativity.

To address these gaps, Design Thinking (DT) offers a promising pedagogical framework. Defined as a human-centered, iterative process involving empathy, ideation, prototyping, and testing, DT encourages learners to approach problems from multiple perspectives and develop innovative solutions (Liedtka & Locatelli, 2023). In educational contexts, it fosters collaboration, critical thinking, and reflective practice, aligning with the Department of Education's emphasis on inquiry-based and contextualized learning (DepEd, 2023). Integrating DT into LAS transforms them into interactive, student-driven tools that actively promote higher-order thinking. Empirical evidence demonstrates its effectiveness in enhancing creative confidence and problem-solving skills (Laurel, 2022), promoting collaboration and innovation, improving engagement and academic achievement, and increasing creativity among Filipino senior high school learners.

Overall, this research investigates the development and implementation of Design Thinking–Based Learning Activity Sheets (DT-LAS) in General Biology for senior high school students. By embedding DT stages into structured learning activities, DT-LAS aim to enhance creativity, deepen conceptual understanding, and promote learner autonomy. This study addresses the persistent research gap in student-centered, higher-order learning while responding to the national call for more relevant and engaging instructional strategies.

Ultimately, the research contributes to science education reform by providing empirical evidence on how DT-LAS can transform traditional learning materials into tools that foster creativity, innovation, and conceptual mastery, supporting the development of 21st-century skills among Filipino learners.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of creativity of students exposed to design thinking-based learning activity sheets and those exposed to non-design thinking-based learning activity sheets in their pretest and posttest in terms of: fluency, flexibility, originality, and elaboration?
2. What is the level of conceptual understanding of students exposed to design thinking-based learning activity sheets and those exposed to non-design thinking-based learning activity sheets in terms of their pretest, and posttest?
3. Is there a significant difference in the creativity of students exposed to design thinking-based learning activity sheets and those exposed to non-design thinking-based learning activity sheets in their pretest and posttest?
4. Is there a significant difference in the conceptual understanding of students exposed to design thinking-based learning activity sheets and those exposed to non-design thinking-based learning activity sheets with pretest as covariate?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quasi-experimental design to examine the effects of Design Thinking–Based Learning Activity Sheets (DT-LAS) on students' creativity and conceptual understanding. Two intact heterogeneous sections of Grade 12 General Academic Strand (GAS) students were selected, with sections randomly assigned to the experimental group (n = 36) using DT-LAS and the control group (n = 38) using Non-Design Thinking–Based Learning Activity Sheets (Non-DT-LAS) through a coin toss. All participants were officially enrolled in Grade 12 GAS during the 2025–2026 school year, and prior academic performance based on the previous Table of Mastery ranged from “not mastered” to “nearly mastered,” establishing baseline knowledge. Informed consent was obtained from both students and their parents, and all responses were kept confidential. Both groups were taught the same competencies, within the same timeframe, and using the same 4As lesson plan to ensure uniform instructional delivery.

The research instruments included a researcher-made conceptual understanding test and an adapted and modified creativity rubric (Widyastuti & Jayanta, 2024). The conceptual understanding test, administered during the first semester midterm, consisted of 50 items covering Cell Theory, Structure and Functions, Cell Types and Modifications, Cell Cycle and Division, Cell Membrane and Transport Mechanisms, and the Structure and Function of Biological Molecules and Enzymes. Both instruments were content validated by four experts, two professors from the Science Department of Central Mindanao University and two master teachers from Science Department of Bukidnon National High School. The conceptual understanding test was pilot tested on former Grade 12 STEM students, yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.94, indicating excellent internal consistency.

Descriptive statistics, including means and standard deviations, were used to summarize students' creativity and conceptual understanding. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was employed to examine significant differences between the experimental and control groups while controlling for pretest scores as covariates. ANCOVA was applied to the creativity dimensions: fluency, flexibility, originality, and elaboration, as well as conceptual understanding. The study was limited to Grade 12 GAS students and specific General Biology 1 topics for the midterm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Students' Creativity in Fluency

Table 1. Pretest and Posttest Creativity Levels in Fluency of Students Exposed to DT-LAS and Non-DT-LAS.

Table 1. Students' Creativity Levels in Fluency in General Biology 1 Exposed to DT-LAS and Non-DT-LAS: Pretest and Posttest Results

Group	Pre-test			Post Test		
	Mean	SD	QI	Mean	SD	QI
DT-LAS	2.55	0.211	MC	4.68	0.209	VHC
Non-DT-LAS	2.42	0.313	LC	3.44	0.304	MC
Legend	Interval	QI				
	4.51-5.00	Very High Creativity (VHC)				
	3.51-4.50	High Creativity (HC)				
	2.51-3.50	Moderate Creativity (MC)				
	1.51-2.50	Low Creativity (LC)				
	1.00-1.50	Very Low Creativity (VLC)				

In the pretest, the DT-LAS group (N = 36) obtained a mean score of 2.55 (SD = 0.211), interpreted as Moderate Creativity (MC), while the Non-DT-LAS group (N = 38) recorded a mean score of 2.42 (SD = 0.313), interpreted as Low Creativity (LC). The distribution of scores indicates that both groups initially demonstrated limited capacity to

generate multiple and varied ideas in biological problem-solving tasks. These findings reflect the limitations of traditional Learning Activity Sheets, which often emphasize procedural exercises and rote memorization, restricting opportunities for ideational fluency and higher-order thinking.

Following the intervention, the posttest results reveal a substantial improvement in both groups. The DT-LAS group achieved a mean score of 4.68 (SD = 0.209), interpreted as Very High Creativity (VHC), whereas the Non-DT-LAS group attained a mean score of 3.44 (SD = 0.304), interpreted as Moderate Creativity (MC). The higher posttest mean of the DT-LAS group suggests that exposure to Design Thinking–Based Learning Activity Sheets significantly enhanced students’ capacity to generate a greater number of relevant and diverse ideas, demonstrating superior ideational fluency compared to the Non-DT-LAS group.

The very low standard deviation in the DT-LAS posttest indicates consistent performance across learners, reflecting the systematic effect of the design thinking framework in fostering creative fluency. In contrast, the Non-DT-LAS group, although showing improvement, exhibited a more constrained range of ideas, likely due to the structured and content-focused nature of traditional LAS. The enhancement in fluency was particularly evident in lessons on Cell Theory and Cell Membrane and Transport Mechanisms, where students generated multiple hypotheses, proposed explanations for cellular interactions, and explored biological phenomena such as osmosis, diffusion, and enzyme activity from multiple perspectives.

These findings align with Widyastuti and Jayanta (2024), who emphasized that fluency represents the breadth of idea generation fostered by design-thinking-based instruction, enabling students to think adaptively during inquiry-driven tasks. Similarly, Kasri et al. (2021) reported that design-thinking-based pedagogies enhance students’ ideational fluency by promoting the generation of varied and innovative responses. Overall, the results demonstrate that DT-LAS effectively cultivates creative fluency, transforming biology learning from a memorization-centered process into a student-centered environment where learners actively engage in idea generation, problem-solving, and scientific reasoning.

Level of Students’ Creativity in Flexibility

Table 2. Pretest and Posttest Creativity Levels in Flexibility of Students Exposed to DT-LAS and Non-DT-LAS.

Table 2. Students’ Creativity Levels in Flexibility in General Biology 1 Exposed to DT-LAS and Non-DT-LAS: Pretest and Posttest Results

Group	Pre-test			Post Test		
	Mean	SD	QI	Mean	SD	QI
DT-LAS	2.56	0.108	MC	4.57	0.241	VHC
Non-DT-LAS	2.83	0.120	MC	3.51	0.214	HC
Legend	Interval		QI			

4.51-5.00	Very High Creativity (VHC)
3.51-4.50	High Creativity (HC)
2.51-3.50	Moderate Creativity (MC)
1.51-2.50	Low Creativity (LC)
1.00-1.50	Very Low Creativity (VLC)

In the pretest, the DT-LAS group (N = 36) obtained a mean score of 2.56 (SD = 0.108), interpreted as Moderate Creativity (MC), while the Non-DT-LAS group (N = 38) recorded a mean score of 2.83 (SD = 0.120), also interpreted as MC. The distribution of scores indicates that both groups initially demonstrated a limited ability to shift perspectives or employ varied approaches in problem-solving tasks. These findings reflect the common limitation of traditional Learning Activity Sheets, which often focus on procedural exercises and rote memorization, thereby restricting opportunities for cognitive flexibility and higher-order thinking.

Following the intervention, the posttest results reveal a notable improvement in both groups. The DT-LAS group achieved a mean score of 4.57 (SD = 0.241), interpreted as Very High Creativity (VHC), whereas the Non-DT-LAS group attained a mean of 3.51 (SD = 0.214), interpreted as High Creativity (HC). The higher posttest mean of the DT-LAS group suggests that engagement with Design Thinking–Based Learning Activity Sheets significantly enhanced students' capacity to consider multiple perspectives, explore alternative approaches, and adapt reasoning strategies, thereby fostering greater creative flexibility.

The low standard deviation in the DT-LAS posttest indicates consistent improvement across participants, reflecting the systematic influence of the design thinking framework in promoting adaptive and multidimensional thinking. In contrast, the Non-DT-LAS group, while showing improvement, displayed a more constrained range of responses, likely due to the structured and content-focused nature of traditional LAS. The development of flexibility was particularly evident in lessons on Cell Membrane and Transport Mechanisms and Structure and Function of Biological Molecules and Enzymes, where students engaged in interdisciplinary exploration, problem-redefinition, and collaborative reasoning.

These findings align with Widyastuti and Jayanta (2024), who identified flexibility as a critical dimension of creativity, representing learners' ability to integrate diverse viewpoints and problem-solving strategies. Similarly, Luthfi and Septiyanti (2023) reported that design-thinking-based pedagogies enhance adaptive and integrative thinking, enabling learners to construct multifaceted explanations of complex phenomena. The results of the present study corroborate these conclusions, confirming that DT-LAS effectively nurtures creative flexibility by engaging students in iterative, inquiry-driven, and collaborative learning experiences, which are essential for meeting the cognitive demands of 21st-century science education.

Level of Students' Creativity in Originality

Table 3. Pretest and Posttest Creativity Levels in Originality of Students Exposed to DT-LAS and Non-DT-LAS.

Table 3. Students' Creativity Levels in Originality in General Biology 1 Exposed to DT-LAS and Non-DT-LAS: Pretest and Posttest Results

Group	Pre-test			Post Test		
	Mean	SD	QI	Mean	SD	QI
DT-LAS	2.49	0.401	LC	4.59	0.143	VHC
Non-DT-LAS	2.42	0.431	LC	3.44	0.102	MC
Legend	Interval		QI			
	4.51-5.00	Very High Creativity (VHC)				
	3.51-4.50	High Creativity (HC)				
	2.51-3.50	Moderate Creativity (MC)				
	1.51-2.50	Low Creativity (LC)				
	1.00-1.50	Very Low Creativity (VLC)				

In the pretest, the DT-LAS group (N = 36) obtained a mean score of 2.49 (SD = 0.401), interpreted as Low Creativity (LC), while the Non-DT-LAS group (N = 38) recorded a mean score of 2.42 (SD = 0.431), also interpreted as LC. The distribution of scores indicates that students in both groups initially demonstrated limited capacity to generate unique or innovative ideas, often following conventional patterns of thinking. These findings reflect the limitations of traditional Learning Activity Sheets, which typically emphasize procedural exercises and rote memorization, thereby restricting opportunities for originality and higher-order thinking.

Following the intervention, the posttest results reveal a notable increase in originality for both groups. The DT-LAS group achieved a mean score of 4.59 (SD = 0.143), interpreted as Very High Creativity (VHC), whereas the Non-DT-LAS group obtained a mean score of 3.44 (SD = 0.102), interpreted as Moderate Creativity (MC). The observed increase in the DT-LAS group, along with the very low standard deviation, suggests consistent improvement across participants, reflecting the effectiveness of the design thinking framework in promoting open-ended, exploratory, and iterative learning experiences. In contrast, the Non-DT-LAS group, while demonstrating some improvement, exhibited a narrower range of creative responses, likely due to the more structured and content-focused nature of traditional LAS.

The posttest results indicate that students exposed to DT-LAS were able to design innovative experiments, create original models, and generate unique explanations for biological phenomena. Through the iterative stages of empathy, ideation, prototyping, and testing, learners engaged in collaborative brainstorming, experimentation, and reflection, thereby enhancing their capacity for divergent and imaginative thinking.

These findings are consistent with Widyastuti and Jayanta (2024), who emphasized that originality reflects the ability to diverge from conventional thinking and produce genuinely novel ideas. Similarly, Zulyusri et al. (2023) reported that design-thinking-based instruction fosters originality by encouraging divergent thinking, learner autonomy, and constructive risk-taking. Overall, the results demonstrate that DT-LAS effectively cultivates originality, equipping students with essential 21st-century competencies for authentic scientific inquiry, creative problem-solving, and innovation.

Level of Students' Creativity in Elaboration

Table 4. Pretest and Posttest Creativity Levels in Elaboration of Students Exposed to DT-LAS and Non-DT-LAS.

Table 4. Students' Creativity Levels in Elaboration in General Biology 1 Exposed to DT-LAS and Non-DT-LAS: Pretest and Posttest Results

Group	Pre-test			Post Test		
	Mean	SD	QI	Mean	SD	QI
DT-LAS	2.54	0.230	MC	4.52	0.198	VHC
Non-DT-LAS	2.58	0.120	MC	3.46	0.177	MC
Legend	Interval	QI				
	4.51-5.00	Very High Creativity (VHC)				
	3.51-4.50	High Creativity (HC)				
	2.51-3.50	Moderate Creativity (MC)				
	1.51-2.50	Low Creativity (LC)				
	1.00-1.50	Very Low Creativity (VLC)				

In the pretest, the DT-LAS group (N = 36) obtained a mean score of 2.54 (SD = 0.230), interpreted as Moderate Creativity (MC), while the Non-DT-LAS group (N = 38) recorded a mean of 2.58 (SD = 0.120), also interpreted as MC. These results indicate that both groups initially demonstrated comparable and moderate levels of elaborative thinking, characterized by limited ability to expand, refine, and organize ideas coherently in scientific contexts. Such limitations reflect common constraints of traditional Learning Activity Sheets, which tend to emphasize procedural tasks and rote memorization rather than opportunities for iterative refinement and detailed reasoning.

Following the intervention, both groups exhibited improvement, with a more pronounced increase among the DT-LAS participants. The DT-LAS group achieved a posttest mean of 4.52 (SD = 0.198), interpreted as Very High Creativity (VHC), while the Non-DT-LAS group attained a mean of 3.46 (SD = 0.177), interpreted as Moderate Creativity (MC). The higher posttest mean of the DT-LAS group demonstrates the effectiveness of Design Thinking-Based Learning Activity Sheets in enhancing students' elaborative skills, particularly in developing, refining, and presenting scientific ideas with clarity, logical sequencing, and depth.

The low standard deviation in the DT-LAS posttest indicates consistent gains across students, suggesting that the iterative processes of ideation, prototyping, testing, and reflection systematically supported elaboration. In contrast, the Non-DT-LAS group exhibited a narrower range of improvement, likely due to limited opportunities for feedback and iterative revision inherent in traditional, content-focused LAS.

Elaborative thinking was particularly evident in lessons on Cell Theory, Structure, and Functions and Cell Membrane and Transport Mechanisms, where DT-LAS participants expanded ideas, integrated theoretical concepts with empirical evidence, and produced logically sequenced explanations. Through the iterative design thinking stages, students refined initial hypotheses into well-developed arguments that connected multiple biological concepts, including organelle functions, molecular transport, and energy flow. These processes fostered precision, depth, and coherence in reasoning, hallmarks of creative elaboration essential for scientific problem-solving and communication.

These findings align with Widyastuti & Jayanta (2024), who defined elaboration as the ability to expand, refine, and organize ideas with clarity and coherence. Similarly, Sudarto et al. (2021) highlighted that design-thinking-based pedagogies enhance reflective reasoning, iterative problem-solving, and collaborative learning, all of which strengthen elaborative capacities in science education. Studies by Rumahlatu et al. (2021) further confirm that integrating design thinking into STEM instruction cultivates structured reflection and deeper engagement, leading to improved creativity and analytical skills.

In summary, the data indicate that Design Thinking–Based Learning Activity Sheets effectively foster elaborative creativity by engaging students in continuous cycles of reflection, revision, and integration of evidence. This pedagogical approach transforms learning from passive content absorption to active knowledge construction, enabling students to produce detailed, coherent, and logically connected scientific explanations. Consequently, DT-LAS emerges as a powerful instructional tool for developing creative elaboration, a key competency for meaningful participation in 21st-century science education.

Level of Students' Overall Creativity

Table 5 presents the overall creativity levels of students exposed to Design Thinking–Based Learning Activity Sheets (DT-LAS) and Non–Design Thinking–Based Learning Activity Sheets (Non-DT-LAS).

Table 5. Students' Overall Creativity Levels in General Biology 1 Exposed to DT-LAS and Non-DT-LAS: Pretest and Posttest Results

Dimension	Pre-test						Post-Test					
	DT-LAS			Non-DT-LAS			DT-LAS			Non-DT-LAS		
	Mean	SD	QI	Mean	SD	QI	Mean	SD	QI	Mean	SD	QI

Fluency	2.55	0.211	MC	2.42	0.313	LC	4.68	0.209	VHC	3.44	0.304	MC
Flexibility	2.56	0.108	MC	2.83	0.120	MC	4.57	0.241	VHC	3.51	0.214	HC
Originality	2.49	0.401	LC	2.42	0.431	LC	4.59	0.143	VHC	3.44	0.102	MC
Elaboration	2.54	0.230	MC	2.58	0.120	MC	4.52	0.198	VHC	3.46	0.177	MC
Weighted Mean	2.54	0.238	MC	2.56	0.246	MC	4.59	0.198	VHC	3.46	0.199	MC
Legend	Interval		QI									
	4.51-5.00		Very High Creativity (VHC)									
	3.51-4.50		High Creativity (HC)									
	2.51-3.50		Moderate Creativity (MC)									
	1.51-2.50		Low Creativity (LC)									
	1.00-1.50		Very Low Creativity (VLC)									

The result presents the pretest and posttest outcomes on the overall level of creativity of students exposed to Design Thinking–Based Learning Activity Sheets (DT-LAS) and Non–Design Thinking–Based Learning Activity Sheets (Non-DT-LAS) in General Biology 1 after the prototype presentation. The students’ creativity levels were determined through the mean scores, standard deviations, and corresponding qualitative interpretations across the four dimensions: fluency, flexibility, originality, and elaboration.

During the pretest, both the DT-LAS and Non-DT-LAS groups demonstrated moderate creativity (MC), with weighted means of 2.54 (SD = 0.238) and 2.56 (SD = 0.246), respectively. This indicates that before the intervention, students in both groups possessed similar creative capacities, able to generate ideas to a moderate extent but lacking depth, variety, and elaboration. The pretest results suggest limited exposure to tasks requiring divergent and innovative thinking, which aligns with the expectation that traditional learning activity sheets often emphasize procedural exercises and rote memorization, restricting opportunities for creativity and higher-order thinking.

Following the intervention, the posttest results revealed a substantial increase in creativity levels among the DT-LAS participants, achieving a very high creativity (VHC) rating with a weighted mean of 4.59 (SD = 0.198). This notable improvement indicates that the DT-LAS approach effectively fostered creative thinking across all four dimensions. Fluency achieved the highest posttest mean (M = 4.68, SD = 0.209), reflecting students’ ability to produce numerous and diverse ideas efficiently. Flexibility (M = 4.57, SD = 0.241) demonstrated the capacity to adapt and shift perspectives when addressing biological problems. Originality (M = 4.59, SD = 0.143) indicated learners’ ability to generate novel and distinctive ideas, while elaboration (M = 4.52, SD = 0.198) reflected enhanced capability to refine and develop ideas with clarity, coherence, and logical organization.

In contrast, the Non-DT-LAS group showed only moderate improvement, attaining an overall weighted mean of 3.46 (SD = 0.199), still within the moderate creativity (MC) category. Among the dimensions, flexibility obtained the highest mean (M = 3.51, SD = 0.214), categorized as high creativity (HC), whereas fluency, originality, and elaboration remained at moderate levels. These results suggest that traditional LAS supported

incremental development in creativity but lacked the iterative, open-ended, and collaborative characteristics essential for fostering higher-order thinking.

Overall, the comparative analysis between pretest and posttest scores demonstrates that the DT-LAS approach significantly enhanced students' creative performance. The pronounced difference between the two groups underscores the effectiveness of design thinking in promoting divergent, flexible, and innovative thinking. Students engaged in DT-LAS exhibited improved ideational fluency, adaptability, originality, and elaboration, confirming that design thinking–based learning cultivates 21st-century creativity skills.

These results align with previous research underscoring the positive impact of design thinking in education. Earlier studies found that design thinking–based instruction enhances ideational fluency and cognitive flexibility through inquiry-oriented and iterative learning processes. Widyastuti and Jayanta (2024) emphasized that design thinking promotes originality by guiding learners to explore, prototype, and refine ideas within authentic contexts. Similarly, Murillo-Zamorano et al. (2021) reported that incorporating design thinking into biology instruction enhances creative performance and deepens conceptual understanding, fostering a more engaging and transformative learning experience.

Level of Students' Conceptual Understanding

Table 6 presents the pretest and posttest results on students' conceptual understanding in General Biology 1 for those exposed to Design Thinking–Based Learning Activity Sheets (DT-LAS) and Non–Design Thinking–Based Learning Activity Sheets (Non-DT-LAS).

Table 6. Students' Conceptual Understanding in General Biology 1 Exposed to DT-LAS and Non-DT-LAS: Pretest and Posttest Results

	Pretest				Post Test			
	DT-LAS		Non-DT-LAS		DT-LAS		Non-DT-LAS	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Mean Percentage Score								
90-100 (Outstanding)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
85-89 (Very Satisfactory)	0	0	0	0	1	2.63	0	0
80-84 (Satisfactory)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
75-79 (Fairly Satisfactory)	0	0	0	0	2	5.26	1	2.78
Below-75 (Did Not Meet Expectations)	38	100	36	100	35	92.11	35	97.22
Total	38	100	36	100	38	100	36	100
Overall MPS	17.74		14.67		28.84		28.89	
Qualitative Interpretation	DNME		DNME		DNME		DNME	

The results indicate that both groups initially demonstrated a low level of conceptual understanding in General Biology 1 during the pretest, with all students classified under the Did Not Meet Expectations (DNME) category. The DT-LAS group obtained an overall mean percentage score (MPS) of 17.74, while the Non-DT-LAS group scored 14.67, reflecting insufficient prior knowledge of the subject. This suggests that both groups began with comparable baseline understanding and required significant instructional support to enhance their conceptual grasp.

Following the implementation of the Design Thinking–Based Learning Activity Sheets (DT-LAS), improvements were observed in both groups. The DT-LAS group achieved a posttest MPS of 28.84, and the Non-DT-LAS group attained 28.89. Despite these gains, scores for both groups remained within the DNME category, indicating that while conceptual understanding increased, it did not reach satisfactory levels. This outcome may be attributed to the nature of design-thinking activities, which emphasize ideation, prototyping, and iterative problem-solving over explicit conceptual discussions (Guaman-Quintanilla et al., 2023).

The low posttest performance suggests that although students were actively engaged, they struggled to organize and integrate biological concepts meaningfully. Within the design-thinking framework, conceptual understanding develops through reflection, analysis, and evidence-based reasoning; however, limited time and structured guidance may have constrained these processes.

These findings align with Cunningham et al. (2020), who observed that traditional assessments may not fully capture conceptual growth achieved through design-based learning. Similarly, Talanquer (2021) emphasized that while design-thinking environments enhance creativity, collaboration, and problem-solving, explicit scaffolding is necessary to translate these skills into deeper conceptual mastery. Overall, the results highlight the need to complement hands-on, creative exploration with structured reflection and evidence-based reasoning to foster meaningful understanding in General Biology 1.

Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Students’ Creativity as exposed to Design Thinking Based Learning Activity Sheets and Non-Design-Thinking Based Learning Activity Sheets

Table 7 presents the ANCOVA results, showing a significant difference in creativity between the DT-LAS and Non-DT-LAS groups after controlling for pretest scores.

Table 7. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the Students’ Creativity in the Posttest

Group	N	Mean	SD
DT-LAS	38	4.59	0.196
Non-DT-LAS	36	3.46	0.193

Source	Type III sum of squares	df	Mean Square	f-value	Sig.
Corrected Model	23.500 ^a	2	11.750	308.867	.000
PRETEST (Covariate)	.018	1	.018	.474	.493
GROUP	23.314	1	23.314	612.847	.000*
Error	2.701	71	.038		
Total	26.201	73			

Legend: Significant at $P < 0.05$

Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on students' creativity of the posttest results for both DT-LAS and Non-DT-LAS groups using the pretest as the covariate. The table shows that the DT-LAS group ($n = 36$, $SD = 0.196$) and Non-DT-LAS group ($n = 38$, $SD = 0.193$) obtained mean creativity scores of 4.59 and 3.46, respectively.

The F-value between groups is 612.847, with a p-value of 0.000*, indicating statistical significance. This result implies that the type of learning activity sheet—Design Thinking–Based Learning Activity Sheets versus Non–Design Thinking–Based Learning Activity Sheets—has a substantial effect on students' creativity in General Biology 1.

The findings highlight the significant positive impact of DT-LAS on students' creative capacities. This aligns with Guaman-Quintanilla et al. (2023), who reported that Design Thinking fosters creativity and problem-solving through iterative, reflective, and student-centered approaches. Similarly, Monreal and Panoy (2023) emphasized that DT-based materials nurture creativity by engaging learners in hands-on, collaborative, and problem-driven activities. The non-significant covariate (pretest) result ($p = 0.493$) confirms that both groups began with comparable levels of creative thinking, indicating that the posttest differences are attributable to the DT-LAS intervention.

Moreover, DT-LAS enhanced performance across all creativity dimensions: fluency, flexibility, originality, and elaboration. Students engaged in multiple idea generation (fluency), perspective-shifting (flexibility), novel idea creation (originality), and iterative refinement (elaboration), consistent with the findings of Boiser-Come et al. (2024) While DT-LAS effectively improved creativity, classroom observations suggested that some learners focused more on prototype design than on conceptual understanding, regarding the need for guided reflection.

Overall, the ANCOVA results confirm that DT-LAS significantly enhances creativity relative to traditional, content-driven learning approaches. These results support global and local studies advocating Design Thinking as a transformative pedagogical strategy that promotes innovation, critical thinking, and adaptive learning among students.

Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Posttest in Students' Conceptual Understanding as exposed to Design-Thinking Based Learning Activity Sheets and Non-Design-Thinking Based Learning Activity Sheets

Table 8 presents the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the students' conceptual understanding in the posttest, with pretest scores as the covariate between groups.

Table 8: ANCOVA for conceptual understanding between DT-LAS and Non-DT-LAS with pre-test score as covariate

Group	N	Mean	SD
DT-LAS	38	28.84	5.544
Non-DT-LAS	36	28.89	4.609

Source	Type III sum of squares	df	Mean Square	f-value	Sig.
Corrected Model	175.914	2	87.957	3.663	.031
PRETEST (Covariate)	175.874	1	175.874	7.325	.009
GROUP	20.758	1	20.758	.865	.356
Error	1704.734	71	24.010		
Total	1880.649	73			

Legend: Significant at $P < 0.05$

Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on students' conceptual understanding of the posttest results for both DT-LAS and Non-DT-LAS groups using the pretest as the covariate. The table shows that the DT-LAS ($n = 38$, $SD = 5.544$) and Non-DT-LAS ($n = 36$, $SD = 4.609$) groups obtained a mean score of 28.84 and 28.89, respectively.

The F-value between groups is 0.865, with a p-value of 0.356, indicating no statistical significance. This result implies that DT-LAS and Non-DT-LAS have similar levels of conceptual understanding in General Biology 1 after controlling for pretest scores.

The findings suggest that while students' pretest scores significantly influenced posttest performance ($F = 7.325$, $p = 0.009$), the type of learning activity sheet—whether DT-LAS or Non-DT-LAS—did not produce a significant effect on conceptual understanding. This aligns with research by Stammes et al. (2023), which emphasizes that design-thinking-based activities enhance engagement, creativity, and problem-solving, but additional structured guidance and reflection are necessary to translate these experiences into meaningful conceptual gains.

These results highlight the need to complement DT-LAS with targeted conceptual scaffolding to strengthen students' understanding of biological concepts, ensuring that creative exploration is effectively integrated with scientific knowledge acquisition.

Conclusions

Findings shows that the level of creativity of students exposed to the Design Thinking–Based Learning Activity Sheets (DT-LAS) demonstrated a substantial increase in their creativity levels from pretest to posttest, progressing from high to very high across all dimensions: fluency, flexibility, originality, and elaboration. In contrast, those exposed to the Non–Design Thinking–Based Learning Activity Sheets (Non-DT-LAS) showed only minimal improvement, remaining at a moderate level of creativity. This indicates that the DT-LAS approach effectively fosters higher-order creative thinking skills and supports significant enhancement in students’ overall creative performance compared to traditional LAS approach.

The level of conceptual understanding revealed that both the DT-LAS and Non-DT-LAS groups showed improvement in their conceptual understanding after instruction; however, their posttest scores remained within the Did Not Meet Expectations range. This indicates that while the Design Thinking–Based Learning Activity Sheets facilitated some enhancement in students’ comprehension, they were not sufficient to bring performance to satisfactory levels. Thus, the DT-LAS approach proved beneficial for stimulating engagement and conceptual awareness but requires further refinement to achieve deeper understanding of biological concepts.

There was a significant difference in creativity between students exposed to the Design Thinking–Based Learning Activity Sheets (DT-LAS) and those using the Non–Design Thinking–Based Learning Activity Sheets (Non-DT-LAS). After controlling for pretest performance, the DT-LAS group achieved higher posttest creativity scores, indicating that the incorporation of design thinking principles effectively enhanced students’ creative abilities in terms of fluency, flexibility, originality, and elaboration. This demonstrates that design-thinking–based instruction provides a more engaging and innovative learning experience compared to traditional approaches.

There was no significant difference in students’ conceptual understanding between those exposed to the Design Thinking–Based Learning Activity Sheets (DT-LAS) and those using Non-DT-LAS. The findings suggest that while design thinking activities encourage engagement, reflection, and exploration, they did not lead to measurable gains in organizing, relating, or applying biological concepts compared to traditional approaches.

Recommendations

Science teachers may integrate Design Thinking–Based Learning Activity Sheets (DT-LAS) into classroom instruction, as these activities have been shown to enhance students’ creativity and engagement. A blended approach is recommended—DT-LAS for hands-on, design-oriented tasks to promote innovation, and concept-focused discussions and guided reflections to reinforce foundational biological principles. By balancing creative exploration with explicit conceptual instruction, students can develop both divergent thinking and a strong understanding of core biology concepts.

As DT-LAS supports multiple dimensions of creativity, schools may provide resources, training, and administrative support to ensure effective implementation. Structured opportunities for ideation, prototyping, and reflection can enhance engagement, while scaffolding strategies and reflective exercises help translate students' active participation into measurable gains in understanding.

Since no significant differences were found in students' conceptual understanding between those exposed to DT-LAS and those using Non-DT-LAS, educational policymakers and curriculum developers may consider integrating Design Thinking–Based Learning Activity Sheets with targeted concept-focused instruction. This approach can help ensure that creative, hands-on activities are effectively paired with explicit teaching of biological concepts, promoting both innovative thinking and measurable gains in understanding.

Future researchers may conduct longitudinal studies with larger and more diverse student samples to examine the long-term effects of DT-LAS on creativity and conceptual understanding. Future research could also compare DT-LAS with purely traditional learning activities to refine instructional recommendations and maximize effectiveness.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research adhered to the ethical guidelines established by the Institutional Ethics Review Committee (IERC) of Central Mindanao University. Prior to the study, the researcher secured permission from the teachers and students, and participants provided informed consent, with the freedom to withdraw at any time without consequences. Anonymity and confidentiality were maintained throughout the study in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, and all collected information was stored securely. The respondents' well-being was always safeguarded. Any potential conflicts of interest were disclosed and addressed, and no plagiarism occurred. The researcher observed ethical conduct at all stages, ensured unbiased interpretation of the findings, and reported results solely for research purposes. No AI tools were used in the preparation or analysis of this study.

Acknowledgments

The researcher sincerely extends her gratitude to all who supported the completion of this master's thesis. She is especially thankful to her adviser, Dr. Maris Jade Q. Orongan, for her guidance, patience, and encouragement, and to Dr. Jenyliza T. Uchang and Prof. Sherwin M. Cupida for their valuable insights and feedback. She also appreciates Dr. Cherry Mae L. Limbaco-Reyes, Dr. Paul O. Orong, Ma'am Emelie Joy P. Idulsa, Dr. Rhesa T. Hinampas, Prof. Ehlich Ray J. Magday, Dr. Mary Jean S. Paraiso, Dr. Barbra Joey P. Moreno, and Ma'am Ethel M. Gayona for their support in facilitating the study and improving its quality. Special thanks go to Ma'am Kezia Keren S. Flores, Dr. Joevi Jhun A. Idul, Ma'am Quenie Mariel I. Jaculbe, Ma'am Joan R. Butong and Ma'am Joan M. Lambo for assistance in data analysis and evaluation. She is grateful to the Grade 12 Duterte and Osmeña students for their cooperation, and to the Gokongwei

Brothers Foundation TeachSTEM Scholarship and various friends and groups for their encouragement. Above all, she owes her deepest love and gratitude to her mother Angelica and sister Crystal Gayle for their unwavering support and to Almighty God for His guidance and blessings throughout this journey. This thesis reflects the collective support received, for which the researcher is genuinely grateful.

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